

Applying Anekāntavāda: A Jaina Perspective on Business Ethics Dilemma

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Abstract

In the present age, the businesses encounter myriad of challenges for its survival, with business ethics playing a pivotal role. While many businesses endeavor to operate ethically, they constantly face dilemmas that challenge their commitment to ethical conduct. In today's globalized world, characterized by heightened connectivity and interdependence, the businesses are under persistent increased pressure to visibly conduct business in a way to balance between its economic interest and ethical principles. The doctrine of *Anekāntavāda*, cornerstone of Jaina philosophy, is the tool through which the Jaina philosophers are able to contend that reality has multiple characteristics. *Anekāntavāda* is the approach of mind which forbids it from viewing any problem or solution from partial view in order to adopt comprehensive view of reality. Where Jainism is known as a one of the religions with ethical principles, this paper is an attempt to investigate how a modern-day businesses can resolve business ethics dilemmas in a peaceful manner by incorporating the theory of *anekāntavāda*. This research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the intersections between ancient wisdom theory and contemporary ethical issues, offering wider insights in the field of business ethics.

Keywords: Business ethics, Jaina philosophy, Truth, *Anekāntavāda*, *Nayavāda*, *Dravyāstika naya*, *Paryāyāstika naya*

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Introduction

Business ethics is the set of moral and ethical values that guide the actions and behaviour in the business environment. There are two important factors which regulate the conduct of business viz. mandatory laws and regulations established by the regulator as the framework within which business must operate and internal policies developed by the business to regulate its relations with internal as well as external stakeholders. It is the picture of how the business operate on a day-to day basis and maintain relations with all its stakeholders along with compliance with corporate regulations and legislations. Internal policies are more subtle and create room for misunderstandings. These internal policies reflect mutual expectations regarding each other's roles, responsibilities, and ethics. If we look at the past, there was time when business and ethics were considered as opposite poles. The only motive of business was to earn profit. But the time has changed completely, now business cannot survive without ethics. However, the fact remains that the relation between profits and ethics is quite tenuous. More often it happens that stakeholders have presumptions that businesses cannot run ethically and therefore most of them would be unethical. One of the most important reasons for such a notion is the ambiguity relating to what actually is ethics. The term ethics may mean differently to each and every individual and depends on individual's view point. Business ethics therefore plays most important role not only in the survival and success of the business but also for mental peace and satisfaction of the stakeholders. However, most of the times business as well as stakeholders are not entirely satisfied because they differ in their view on what is right and what is wrong. In reality, truth is a very complex notion and has many realms. On one hand, Absolute truth gives clear and precise understanding of the thing itself by discarding any doubts which comes at the cost of repudiating its contrary. Whereas Relative truth is based on the individual's understanding of it. Relativism and absolutism thus have their own merits and demerits. The doctrine of *Anekāntavāda* often cited as the differentia that represents the Jaina philosophical position, is the tool that describes that reality has multiple characteristics. This theory of non-absolutism believes that a particular thing or an object will look differently from different angles but is ultimately same. A particular problem will look different from different perspective from which it is seen. *Anekāntavāda* proposes that reality has many forms as seen by various individuals and all must respect the reality perceived by one-another and thereby helps in resolving conflicts and increasing tolerance.

Understanding Jaina doctrine of *Anekāntavāda*

Though there were traces of the doctrine of *Anekāntavāda* in the texts composed before Ācārya Siddhasena Diwākara, he was perhaps the first one to use the term *anekāntavāda* and identifying the Jaina position with it. Ācārya Samantabhadra, a stalwart in Jaina logic and epistemology, is credited of having employed the doctrine of *anekāntavāda* to quite a few debates across all the branches of philosophy. The term '*anekāntavāda*' consist of '*aneka*' which means multiple or more than one, '*anta*' which means aspects or qualities and '*vada*' which means theory. Any entity has three aspects viz. *dravya* (substance), *guna* (attributes) and *paryāya* (modes) which means any substance has innumerable attributes which undergoes constant modification. It is not possible for any ordinary person to know all of attributes of any substance or entity at any given point of time. To know all the aspects of any substance at all times is achieving omniscience. *Anekāntavāda* consists of many-sided approach to the study of the problems. It lays emphasis on many-sidedness of the truth. *Anekāntavāda* refers to evaluating a situation or thing from every possible standpoints and fostering a mindset conducive to such analysis. Reality can be viewed from various view points and every viewpoint has an element of truth, and we can get to know the truth only when all viewpoints are amalgamated.

Naya is the valid knowledge of one part, aspect or quality of the reality and since any reality can be viewed from many angles there are multiple naya or standpoints. The theory of *Nayavāda* classifies the various viewpoints broadly into seven categories viz. *Naigama naya*, *Samgraha naya*, *Vyavhāra naya*, *Rjusūtra naya*, *Śabda naya*, *Samabhirūdhā naya* and *Evambhūta naya*. However, Ācārya Siddhasena Diwākara in the third verse of Sanmati Tarka states that the Dravyāstika naya and Paryāyāstika naya are the two fundamental viewpoints that cover the general and the particular viewpoints of the things. All the other analytical methods of inquiry fall under these two methods only. This also suggests that there are many kinds of views i.e. versatility of aspects however, the same is broadly classified in the abovementioned two views. Dravyāstika naya refers to the perspective that considers the substance or the actual nature of things, while Paryāyāstika naya pertains to the viewpoint that focuses on the aspects or attributes of things. Whenever a person thinks or speaks it either consider the actual nature or the similarity or the present aspect or difference. The exposition of the two nayas and their mutual reconciliation is *Anekānta*.

As stated earlier, any entity has three aspects viz. *dravya* (substance), *guna* (attributes) and *paryāya* (modes). The substance is permanent, constant and unchanging, the modes undergo

constant modification and attributes enables a substance to assume any particular form or mode. From the viewpoint of Paryāyāstika naya all the things necessarily born and perish whereas from the viewpoint of Dravyāstika naya all the things exist eternally without any birth or decay. So, there cannot be anything devoid of modification of birth and death as well as there can be no modification in the absence of the existence. Therefore, birth, decay and continuity are the three characteristics of any substance. The three characteristics must be considered in harmony to understand the truth holistically and to vanish the drawbacks which are attached to every viewpoint severally. If any of these are considered individually it would be incorrect representation or representation of partial truth. Thus, any theory when not based on *Anekānta dr̥ṣṭi* can never ensure perfect or complete knowledge. When all the viewpoints are considered in synthesis it results in broadmindedness rather than narrowmindedness. Therefore, both the viewpoints need to be considered together to arrive at the truth by the method of *Anekāntavāda*. However, the problem arises when one considers only one viewpoint without regard to the other.

Business ethics and its Dilemma

According to Britannica, the term ethics may refer to the philosophical study of the concepts of moral right and wrong and moral good and bad, to any philosophical theory of what is morally right and wrong or morally good and bad, and to any system or code of moral rules, principles, or values. It can be said that ethics deals with social values which makes distinction between what is good or bad. When the term business is prefixed to it, the two collectively refer to right and wrong of the businesses.

Business ethics is thus a form of applied ethics which deals with application of ethics to overall conduct of business including various issues faced by itself and its stakeholders. The object is to prevent unethical business practices, both deliberate and inadvertent. Some unethical practices evade law enforcement. Unlike personal ethics, company rules and regulations are intricate and its non-compliance may result in the organization suffering huge losses. Business ethics includes but is not limited to corporate responsibility, personal responsibility, social responsibility, fairness, respect, reliability and technology ethics. It emphasizes customer loyalty, reputation and employee retention. However, the problem arises because the meaning of the term differs from person to person and organization to organization and everyone has their own view. The application of ethics highly depends on personal ethics of the top

management of the business because what is good or bad depends on the policies and procedures developed by them.

Application of *Anekāntavāda* in Business Ethics dilemmas

The application of the doctrine of *Anekāntavāda* in day to day life facilitates reconciliation of the multiple views of reality. The scope of business ethics is quite wide as ethical problems and phenomena arise across all the functional areas and at all levels within an organization. To prevent any unethical issue, the business organization need to first of all know who are its stakeholders (internal as well as external), know their claims and expectations, weigh their expectations, ethically decide on the action required. Therefore, the task before the business organization is to understand these multiple expectations which may be sometimes conflicting and prioritise amongst them. Again, these expectations are to be weighed against the goals, vision and expectations of the business itself of return on investment, profit, expansion, goodwill, productivity, optimum utilization of resources, healthy cashflow, etc. thus, adopting an approach of holistically considering all the requirements and expectations at various level helps in having broader vision and better decision making. The decision-making process adopted by the business organization for fulfilling the expectation while running usual business is usually unstructured or only loosely structured which leads to problems. This may lead to stakeholders' dissatisfaction and invite unnecessary problems for the business organization like damage to its reputation, potential negative impact on customer retention and loyalty, negative publicity, wide-spread loss of motivation and low productivity amongst employees. *Anekāntavāda* is the approach of mind which forbids it from viewing any problem or solution from one angle or with partial view as one sided angle cannot give comprehensive view of reality and lead to breeding of discontent and hatred. Its states that any affirmation or judgement is true in its own limited sense and is not absolute. Thus, it is imperative for the top management adopt multidimensional approach as a core leadership attribute in order to effectively manage stakeholders with diverse personalities, abilities, expectations, and inclinations.

Also, one of the other important theories which needs attention is the theory of '*Samvāya*' which is the theory of causation. Every action that takes place have deep connection with five main causes together known as *samvāya*. 1) Time (*kāl*), 2) Own-nature (*svabhāva*), 3) *Karma*, 4) Fate (*niyati*) and 5) Self-effort (*prushārtha*) that are responsible for all the things that happen in this universe. Looking at any one of the five causes while considering any event or situation

is considered as *mithya dr̥ṣṭi*. When all these causes are considered on a common ground of synthesis, the cause behind any event become true and significant. However, when any cause is considered in isolation, there is contradiction and imperfectness. Therefore, it is pertinent to consider all the causes while looking at any issue and making decision over it. As a basic notion, every individual has restricted vision wherein it develops *rāga* (attachment) and *dveṣa* (aversion) leading to irrational and sentimental preferences and prejudices while handling any situation. This stops that individual from looking at the situation neutrally considering all the aspects of reality. The task of *Anekāntavāda* is to lead the individuals specially the top management free from *rāga* and *dveṣa* towards more rational way of thinking and decision making.

Further, it is true that although the broad framework remains the same, meaning of the term ethics differs from person to person and organisation to organisation. The goal of each and every stakeholder is different and some are conflicting and non fulfilment results in hatred, depression, mental stress, loss and other negative impacts. But when a stakeholder or business considers all possible views of other stakeholders each of which is true and limited in its own way, and post that takes any decision or action, it will result in satisfaction amongst atleast majority if and not all stakeholders. This does not necessarily mean that views of all stakeholders are valid as *anekāntavāda* states that each view is a partial truth and therefore *anekāntavāda* will only aid in being broad minded and consider different views before coming to any conclusion. This will help in resolving a lot of conflicts beforehand.

Conclusion

The stability of an organisation is put to risk when any unexpected problem occurs and India has been increasingly witnessing turmoil in business and corporate world. Some of the high profile corporate fiascos include that of Satyam Computers, Ketna Parikh's fraud, Harshad Mehta's fraud, Kingfisher Airlines, Jet Airways and so on. False accounting entries, money laundering, fraudulent trades for profit inflation, disclosure of price-sensitive information and such negative activities are growing rapidly. Looking at the case history it can be determined that personal ethics of higher management team and decision making process were some of the important causes of such frauds. Thus, in order to combat such unhealthy practices it is beneficial that higher management team design internal policies and code of conduct for the organization keeping in mind the doctrine of *Anekāntavāda*.

Sometimes, it may happen that we might not agree with everything and everyone, but the idea is to be tolerant. We may have our own mind but at the same time we respect and recognize view of others. One must stand for their own beliefs and opinions if that they are based upon rational observations, but tolerate those of others to have their own. *Anekāntavāda* can greatly be helpful in cultivating such an attitude.

The concepts and theories of Jainism have practical importance in shaping strong ethical business model. Jainism is not just about attaining liberation but it shows various ways and gives direction for the same. This paper brings out the importance of Jaina concept in building healthy ethical model for any business organization which may also result into mental, economic, physical and spiritual well being to individuals. This paper was an attempt to lay down a basic framework on the application of Jaina theory to resolving business ethics dilemma. However, future study can focus on specific key issues faced in business ethics by the top management and skillful application of Jaina theory of *Anekāntavāda* as well as other Jaina values.

Bibliography

1. Pandit Sanghvi S. & Pandit Doshi B.(1939) '*Siddhasen Sen Divakar's Sanmati Tarka with critical Introduction and An original Commentary*' Banares: India Press Ltd.
2. Abhaydevsuri (2010) '*Sanmati Tarka Prakaran-5*' Dholka: Divya Darshan Trust
3. Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia (2019, November 18). *What is ethics?*. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/question/What-is-ethics>
4. William L. (1964) "*An Introduction to Ethics*" University Paperbacks, London.
5. Dr. Jain S and Dr. Pandey S. (1999) '*Multidimensional Application of Anekāntavāda*'. Varanasi: Parswanatha Vidyapitha & Ahmedabad: Navin Institute of Self-development
6. Shah.A.A. R. (2017). *Jainism and Ethical Finanace: A Timless Business Model*. London and New York: Routledge Taylor and Finance Group.
7. David V. (1988). *Ethics and Profit Don't Always go Hand in Hand*. Los Angeles Times (p.7)

8. D. Bhargava, Mardia. K. V. (1968). *Jaina Ethics*. Delhi: Motilal Banarasidass
9. Padmarajiah Y J.. (1963). *A Comparative Study of Jaina Theories of Reality and Knowledge*. Bombay: Jain Sahitya Vikas Mandal
10. Patel, M. R., & Selvaraj., P. (2015). *Role of sociocultural factors in the entrepreneurial success of the Jain community*. International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management, 10(3), (pp.291-305)
11. Matilal, B. K. (1981) *The Central Philosophy of Jainism (Anekāntavāda)*. Ahmedabad: L.D. Institute of Indology.
12. Balmer, J. M. T., Fukukawa, K., & Gray, E. R. (2007). *The Nature and Management of Ethical Corporate Identity: A Commentary on Corporate Identity, Corporate Social Responsibility and Ethics*. Journal of Business Ethics, 76(1) (pp. 7–15)
13. Friedman M., (1970), *The social responsibility of business is to increase its profits*. New York Times Magazine (pp. 32-33, 122, 124, 126)
14. Shah, A. K. (2007). *Jain Business Ethics, Accountancy Business and the Public Interest*6(2).
15. Fairfield, P. (1995). *Overcoming the Theory/Practice Opposition in Business Ethics*. Business & Professional Ethics Journal, 14(4), pp. 23–42. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/27800985>
16. Tota I., Shehu H., (2012). *The Dilemma of Business Ethics*, Procedia Economics and Finance, 3 (pp. 555-559)
17. Taesch, C. F. (1932). *Business Ethics*. International Journal of Ethics, 42(3) (pp.273–288). <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2989578>
18. Dimmock, M., & Fisher, A. (2017). Business Ethics. In Ethics for A-Level (1st ed., pp. 143–155). Open Book Publishers. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt1wc7r6j.12>
19. Marques, J. (2019). *Buddhism and Business Ethics*. In: Poff, D., Michalos, A. (eds) Encyclopedia of Business and Professional Ethics. Springer, Cham. http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23514-1_550-1